

Study on some metal(III) complexes with pyrazine-2-carboxylic and pyridine-2-carboxylic acids

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Complexes of Cr^{III}, Co^{III}, Al^{III} and Bi^{III} with pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid along with some of their picolinates have been synthesized. The ligands are bidentate coordinating through a heterocyclic ring nitrogen and a carboxyl oxygen. A single crystal X-ray analysis on Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃ reveals the structure as highly distorted octahedral, Cr sitting at the center and surrounded by the bidentate ligand.

Bivalent metal complexes containing heterocyclic carboxylic acids derived from pyridine, pyrazine and their homologous ring systems have been extensively studied¹ in respect of their nature of bonding, thermal and magnetic behavior. Much less study has, however, been reported²⁻⁴ involving trivalent metal ions (V, Co, Al, Ga, In, Ln) and pyridine/quinoline carboxylic acid, and little⁵ with pyrazine/quinoxaline carboxylic acids.

The present paper describes synthesis of Cr^{III}, Co^{III}, Al^{III} and Bi^{III} complexes (1-7) with pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid along with some of their picolinates (Figs. 1 and 2). The complexes have been characterized through elemental analysis, magnetic, spectral and thermal study. A single crystal X-ray diffraction study on Cr^{III}-pyrazinate is also described. Attempts to grow single crystals were not successful for other complexes where some crystal parameters were evaluated (except Al^{III}) through X-ray powder diffraction experiments.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are non-hygroscopic, stable at room temperature. They are insoluble in water and common organic solvents including DMSO and DMF. Analytical and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Infrared spectra of both free pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid and picolinic acid show sharp carbonyl absorption around 1700 cm⁻¹, bands observed in their complexes at 1650–1630 and 1395–1330 cm⁻¹ may be tentatively assigned⁶ as

Table 1. Analytical, physical and spectral data of complex*				
Compd./ Colour	Mag. mom. B.M.	% Metal : Found (Calcd.)	% Mass loss : Found (Calcd.) ^d [Temp. range, °C]	λ _{max} cm ⁻¹
Cr(Pz-2- COO) ₃ (1) Red	3.89	12.91 (12.35)	81.0 (82.3) [29.5–524.5]	22200 ^b , 18900 ^c
Co(Pz-2- COO) ₃ (2) Purple	Diamag.	13.07 (13.79)	81.6 (82.0) [30.2–398]	25600 ^d , 18000 ^e
Bi(Pz-2- COO) ₃ .H ₂ O (3) White	–	39.75 (35.06)	53.6 (60.9) [28.3–389]	–
Cr(Py-2- COO) ₃ .H ₂ O (4) Red	3.73	12.38 (11.92)	81.9 (82.6) [25.7–479.6]	23800 ^b , 19200 ^c
Co(Py-2- COO) ₃ .H ₂ O (5) Purple	Diamag.	12.98 (13.31)	79.9 (81.2) [25.3–462.7]	25600 ^d , 19000 ^e
Bi(Py-2- COO) ₃ (6) White	–	35.97 (36.22)	59.8 (59.5) [26.5–432]	–
Al(Pz-2-COO) (OH) ₂ .3H ₂ O (7) White	–	11.21 (11.34)	76.8 (78.6) [24.9–498.6]	–

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

^aInitial to oxide level, M₂O₃/Co₃O₄.

^b⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(F), ^c⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F), ^d¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g}, ^e¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g}.

the asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of coordinated carboxylate anions. A separation by more than 200 cm⁻¹ for the two OCO⁻ stretching vibrations indicates monodentate carboxylate coordination. In the complexes, positive shift (Δν~15–20 cm⁻¹) from the free ligand values in the region 400–450 cm⁻¹ in the frequencies of out-of-plane ring deformation vibration suggests⁶ coordination

through heterocyclic ring nitrogen. Unlike **4** and **5** which give sharp doublet near 3500 cm^{-1} , medium-strong/strong broad band covering $3000\text{--}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed for **3** and **7**, indicating their hydrated nature⁶. The broadness, however, cannot be used to determine whether the water is coordinate or crystalline. Mass-loss study (shown below) may not suggest all crystalline water; any conclusion, however, is forbidden in view of the previous reports⁷. Presence of OH band in the aluminium complex is confused in the complexity of spectra.

Electronic spectra of Cr^{III}- and Co^{III}-pyrazinates as well as picolinates exhibit bands which may be assigned to transitions (Table 1) in an octahedral environment⁸.

TG curves reveal that Cr^{III}- and Co^{III}-picolinates are monohydrates, losing water (found ~4%, calcd. ~5%) at 70–150°; the pyrazinates are anhydrous. Cr^{III}-pyrazinate is thermally a little more stable than the picolinate; the latter begins to decompose earlier (370°) than the pyrazinate (390°) and in course rapidly reaching the oxide level – the picolinate doing at 480° and the pyrazinate at ~525°. The anhydrous Co^{III} complexes of both the ligands remain stable upto ~300°, beyond which decomposition occurs in overlapping steps until the advent of the oxide (Co₃O₄) level at ~400° for the pyrazinate and ~460° for the picolinate. Bi^{III}-picolinate is anhydrous and stable upto ~300°, while the Bi^{III}-pyrazinate contains a molecule of water which is slowly lost (found 4.1%, calcd. 3.0%) at 170–300°. Rapid mass-loss occurs involving intermediates at 300–390° for Bi^{III}-pyrazinate and at 300–430° for Bi^{III}-picolinate to reach the Bi₂O₃ level. The aluminum complex conforms to the trihydrate losing total water (found 23.5%, calcd. 22.8%) through initial rapid steps at 25–138° concurrently followed by a slower one upto ~270°; further mass-loss occurs rapidly thereafter until the oxide level is reached at ~500°.

Single crystal X-ray data of Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃ are given in Tables 2 and 3, together with refinement details. X-ray diffraction study reveals the structure (Fig. 3) as highly distorted octahedral, Cr sitting at the center is surrounded by an approximately octahedral arrangement of three pyrazine N and three carboxylate O atoms from the bidentate ligands. The angles O-Cr-O and O-Cr-N (~95°) are far away from 90° and the *trans* groups N-Cr-N, O-Cr-N and O-Cr-O have deviated to a great extent from linearity. The mean Cr-N and Cr-O bond distances are 2.04 and 1.95 Å, respectively.

Crystallographic study on a number of bivalent and trivalent metal complexes with NO-donor ligands have been reported in literature^{2,9–11}. The octahedral complexes [M^{II}(PzA)₂(OH₂)₂] (M^{II} = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) with pyrazine-2-carboxylate ion (PzA⁻) are characterized¹¹ as monomeric molecules composed of a metal ion, two bidentate pyrazine-2-carboxylate moieties and two water molecules; the coordinated water molecules are involved in extensive network of hydrogen bonding. The mean M-N,

Fig. 3. View of molecular structure of Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃ showing the atom numbering scheme. Hydrogen atoms are not shown for clarity.

M-O bond distances are 2.310, 2.130; 2.094, 2.094; 2.030, 2.068; 1.987, 1.977; and 2.080, 2.097 Å, respectively. The bivalent Mn^{II} octahedral complexes, [MnL₂(OH₂)₂], with quinoline-2-carboxylate and pyridine-2-carboxylate anions (L = QA⁻ and PyA⁻) reportedly^{9,10} show Mn-N and Mn-O bond distances as 2.31, 2.13, and 2.28, 2.15 Å, respectively. The marked decrease in bond lengths in the Cr^{III}-complex compared to the Mn^{II}-complexes are due to higher charge on the metal.

Table 2. Crystal data and structure refinement for Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃

Empirical formula	C ₁₅ H ₉ CrN ₆ O ₆	
Formula weight	421.28	
Temperature	293(2) K	
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	
Crystal system	Monoclinic	
Space group	C2/c	
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 28.421(3)$ Å	$\alpha = 90^\circ$
	$b = 8.1153(9)$ Å	$\beta = 90.271(6)^\circ$
	$c = 13.8934(13)$ Å	$\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	$3204.4(5)$ Å ³	
Z	8	
Density (calculated)	1.746 Mg m ⁻³	
Absorption coefficient	0.767 mm ⁻¹	
$F(000)$	1704	
Crystal size	$0.08 \times 0.44 \times 0.38$ mm ³	
Theta range for data collection	2.61 to 27.50°	
Index ranges	$0 < h < 36, -10 < k < 0, -18 < l < 18$	
Reflections collected	3747	
Independent reflections	3675 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.0247$]	
Completeness to theta = 27.50°	99.9%	
Absorption correction	SHELXA	
Max. and min. transmission	0.8938 and 0.6383	
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2	
Data/restraints/parameters	3765/0/263	
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.016	
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0381, wR2 = 0.0887$	
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0600, wR2 = 0.0983$	
Extinction coefficient	0.00031(13)	
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.257 and -0.336 e. Å ⁻³	

Table 3. Selected bond lengths(Å) and angles(°) of Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃

Bond length (Å)		Angle (°)	
Cr-O(21)	1.9356(16)	O(11)-C(15)	1.295(3)
Cr-O(31)	1.9383(17)	O(12)-C(15)	1.211(3)
Cr-O(11)	1.9564(17)	N(11)-C(14)	1.338(3)
Cr-N(21)	2.042(2)	N(11)-C(11)	1.340(3)
Cr-N(11)	2.058(2)	N(12)-C(13)	1.324(4)
Cr-N(31)	2.0723(19)	N(12)-C(12)	1.336(4)
		C(11)-C(15)	1.509(4)
O(21)-Cr-O(31)	92.61(7)	O(21)-Cr-N(31)	173.13(7)
O(21)-Cr-O(11)	95.29(7)	O(31)-Cr-N(31)	80.53(7)
O(31)-Cr-O(11)	171.38(7)	O(11)-Cr-N(31)	91.57(7)
O(21)-Cr-N(21)	81.37(8)	N(21)-Cr-N(31)	98.56(8)
O(31)-Cr-N(21)	92.14(8)	N(11)-Cr-N(31)	90.28(8)
O(11)-Cr-N(21)	92.45(7)	C(15)-O(11)-Cr	118.26(16)
O(21)-Cr-N(11)	90.64(7)	O(12)-C(15)-O(11)	126.1(3)
O(31)-Cr-N(11)	95.84(8)	O(12)-C(15)-C(11)	120.2(2)
O(11)-Cr-N(11)	80.65(8)	O(11)-C(15)-C(11)	113.7(2)
N(21)-Cr-N(11)	168.96(8)	C(14)-N(11)-C(11)	118.2(2)
C(11)-N(11)-Cr	112.23(16)	C(14)-N(11)-Cr	129.45(19)

In the octahedral Ga^{III}-quinaldinate complex⁴, Ga₂(QA)₄(μ-OH)₂, the mean Ga-N and Ga-O bond distances (with respect to the organic ligand) are 2.12–2.13 and 1.94–1.96 Å, respectively, while in the V^{III}-picolinate complex¹⁰, [V(PyA)₃].H₂O, the respective V-N and V-O distances, are 2.13 and 1.95 Å.

The unit cell of Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃ contains eight molecules to form C-centered monoclinic C_{2c} space group. The unit cell is devoid of any H-bonding and the units are held by weak van der Waals force.

X-Ray powder diffraction spectra of the complexes (2-6) correspond to none of the simple systems, namely, cubic, tetragonal, orthorhombic and hexagonal as revealed on preliminary inspection, and hence Ito's general method of indexing was used to obtain crystal parameters (Table 4). All the complexes show single phase; complex 5 does, however, have more than one phase and a few of the peaks could not be satisfactorily assigned by the Miller indices.

Experimental

Pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid (Fluka) and pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (Schuchardt) were used as such. CrCl₃.6H₂O (AnalaR) was used. Na₂[Co(CO₃)₃].3H₂O and (BiO)₂CO₃ were prepared by reported methods¹².

Cr(Pz-2-COO)₃ (1) : To CrCl₃.6H₂O (250 mg, 1.0 mmol) in water (20 ml) was added pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid (750 mg, 6.0 mmol) and urea (2 g). The solution was heated over a spirit lamp (but not boiled) to liberate ammonia. The green solution turned red, and the red crystals that separated after a week were filtered, washed with water and dried in air. Single crystal suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis was used.

Co(Pz-2-COO)₃ (2) : To pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid (670 mg, 5.4 mmol) in hot water (50 ml) was added Na₃[Co(CO₃)₃].3H₂O (500 mg, 1.39 mmol) portionwise. The resulting solution was immediately filtered. Purple crystals that separated were filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

Bi(Pz-2-COO)₃.H₂O (3) : [(BiO)₂CO₃] (200 mg, 0.39 mmol) suspended in hot water (50 ml) was treated with pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid (100 mg, 0.8 mmol) and stirred for 1 h. Strong effervescence occurred and a white crystalline product appeared when another portion of the ligand (100 mg, 0.8 mmol) was added to the hot suspension. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and dried in air.

Cr(Py-2-COO)₃.H₂O (4), Co(Py-2-COO)₃.H₂O (5) and Bi(Py-2-COO)₃ (6) were prepared as per the procedures of 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Al(Pz-2-COO)(OH)₂.3H₂O (7) : Al(NO₃)₃.9H₂O (375 mg, 1 mmol) was treated with aqueous ammonia (1 : 1), and the precipitated Al(OH)₃ washed by decantation technique was treated with pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid (500 mg, 4 mmol) and stirred for a couple of hours on a hot-plate. The gelatinous precipitate dissolved out to give a granular mass which was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

Infrared spectra (KBr) and electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1330 and Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometers, respectively. Magnetic moment at room temperature was determined by Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as standard. Chromium was determined volumetrically, and cobalt, bismuth and aluminium were determined gravimetrically by the usual procedures. C, H, N were analysed at Indian Association for the Cultivation

Table 4. Lattice parameters of complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	α (°)	β (°)	γ (°)	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	ρ _{calc} (ρ _{expt})	Z
1.	Cr(Py-2-COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	105.86	97.47	89.91	8.34	7.77	7.22	445.98	1.645 (1.644)	1
2.	Co(Pz-2-COO) ₃	123.08	90.78	104.66	7.69	8.83	8.17	437.63	1.638 (1.636)	1
3.	Co(Py-2-COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	110.78	101.50	112.30	9.47	8.96	7.89	445.98	1.645 (1.643)	1
4.	Bi(Pz-2-COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	137.44	90.21	114.49	13.13	15.40	11.17	1202.32	3.32 (3.31)	4
5.	Bi(Py-2-COO) ₃	115.57	96.06	124.32	15.31	15.14	11.78	1797.38	2.152 (2.155)	4

of Science, Kolkata. Thermal data were obtained using Shimadzu-TG-50 instrument with a heating rate of 10° per min at Central Glass and Ceramics Research Institute, Kolkata. X-Ray powder diffraction experiments were carried out using a Rigaku miniflex CN 2005 instrument with $\text{CuK}\alpha = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$ in Department of Physics, University of Kalyani. The single monochromator was obtained at scanning speed (2θ) of 1/2 deg per min. Specific gravity was measured using a glass bottle.

X-Ray crystallography : Crystals of $\text{Cr}(\text{Pz-2-COO})_3$ were glued to the ends of a thin glass fiber and transferred to a Siemens P4/S diffractometer using $\text{MoK}\alpha$ and graphite monochromator. Cell dimensions and an orientation matrix for data collection were obtained from least-squares refinement of the setting angles of at least 25 accurately centered reflections. The structures were solved by direct methods using the SHELXTL package of computer program¹³. Neutral atom scattering factors were used¹⁴ with corrections for real and imaginary anomalous dispersion¹⁵. All structures were refined by full-matrix least-square methods based on F^2 using SHELXTL-96¹⁶ and used all unique data. Non-hydrogen atoms were located in difference Fourier syntheses and refined isotropically. Additional material available from the authors comprises of hydrogen atom coordinates, complete set of bond distances and angles, atomic coordinates and anisotropic displacement parameters.

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